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**METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING INDEPENDENT LEARNING SKILLS IN
STUDENTS OF FUTURE ENGLISH TEACHERS.**

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ABSTRACT

The article explains the following: the core ideas of "independent education," how to effectively organize it for students in higher education, how to foster independent thinking in students, how to help them master various levels of complexity in assignments, and how to foster creative and independent problem-solving in students as they complete practical tasks both inside and outside of the classroom that is grounded in theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and issues related to skill formation.

KEYWORDS: Student, higher education, need, ability, formation; independent education, self-education, independent study; practical skills; independent thinking; creative thinking.

INTRODUCTION

The Republic of Uzbekistan's education system has undergone reforms, and one of the goals of higher education is to better prepare future specialists for self-development, increase their capacity for independent learning, and make extensive use of innovative activities. Of course, completing the task at hand will require more than just the teacher's knowledge. As a result, by planning their independent work, students' independent learning will receive extra attention in the upcoming years.

The training of personnel who possess autonomous and creative thought processes is given significant attention in the educational process. Training youth in general professional subjects, cultivating their desire to learn, enhancing their aptitudes, knowledge, and skills, obtaining their desired careers, and efficiently planning their autonomous and creative work are among the pressing issues that need to be addressed. Our nation needs experts who can think independently and who have acquired comprehensive thinking across a range of disciplines. It is imperative that educators teach their students to think critically on their own during the learning process.

A student should always be able to think independently, regardless of their educational level. The pinnacle of a student's mental development is thought to be thinking or reasoning

LITERATURE REVIEW

Students review the topics they have studied and consult supplementary literature when pursuing independent education. A lot of students prepare lectures and abstracts by working on the lecture texts that were delivered at home and by consulting popular scientific periodicals.

Each educational task must be introduced to the student in terms of its form and type, including written essays, reports, abstracts, etc., oral presentations, question-answering, etc., and the qualitative and quantitative criteria used to evaluate them.

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The task (test, question, task, and exercise) that is suggested for each training session guarantees current pedagogical control and ongoing self-evaluation of the degree of achievement of the learning objectives as perceived by the student.

A. Zimnyaya asserts that independent work is the most important type of education and should be given precedence.

According to the psychology of activity, we can distinguish between the following stages in the order that M.A. Fedorova emphasizes: developing a motive, setting a goal, forming a goal and solving an educational task, operations, and actions, monitoring results, doing and analyzing.

M.B. Balikaeva demonstrated that students' self-education activities depend on their ability to work independently and develop fundamental competencies. According to the author, students' primary competencies consist of systematized knowledge, skills, and abilities that support their acquisition of experience in independent knowledge activities and help them solve a variety of cognitive and educational problems.

The following criteria can be used to determine the levels of independent educational activities based on the way the process of independent education is carried out, how it develops, and what knowledge is acquired:

- independent education in a goal-oriented, motivational environment;
- skills that provide an independent thinking process;
- skills aimed at organizing independent educational activities.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The curriculum of educational institutions, as well as the program designed for all academic and specialized subjects in higher education, now includes a special place for students' independent education.

Definitions of independent education were developed based on scientific research findings. Self-directed learning is a methodical process that aims to develop theoretical understanding, practical abilities, and credentials through self-directed learning of various levels of difficulty, as well as creative and autonomous completion of practical tasks both inside and outside of the classroom. Self-contained pieces vary from one another based on the task, didactic goal, degree of complexity, and target audience (individual or team).

The standard of education is determined by how well and quickly students complete their learning tasks.

In addition to understanding the goal of the training session, students should be aware of the potential educational outcomes when working independently.

Individual topics included in the working curriculum are given to students for independent mastery based on the subject's nature, their level of knowledge, and their abilities. In this situation, it's important to concentrate on fundamental terms that convey and make clear the topic's core ideas, questions that methodically outline the subject, and references to the primary literature and information sources.

The following management actions of the teacher are determined by the student's successful movement of each element indicated in the activity system during their independent work: planning, organizing, monitoring, and evaluation.

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When a teacher establishes guidelines for a student's educational activity, the material is enhanced.

The primary resource in the early stages of independent education is a passion for science. However, this interest won't be intense enough. There isn't any independent, systematic, special organizational, goal-oriented learning going on.

Students independently (relatively, of course) set objectives and tasks for themselves, comprehend the material of independent activities, and complete organizational tasks in the second stage of independent educational activity. Students use this time to complete professional assignments in order to fulfill their personal goals and aspirations. In the second stage, they develop a serious interest in independent work, learn a distinct area of science, use it to create their own personal life plans and prioritize obtaining a profession.

Students who reach the third stage of independent education will have been studying on their own for a number of years and will be able to articulate their career objectives and activities with clarity.

Four categories of independent works are identified in scientific pedagogical literature: samples-based independent works, reconstructive-variation independent works, heuristic (partially creative) independent works, and independent works with a creative research bent. They do not, however, address verifying, dissecting, combining, assessing, or formulating conclusions regarding the outcomes of the aforementioned independent work.

We also believe that there is significant pedagogical value in the analysis and synthesis of the findings of independent creative research. It was discovered that in addition to content creation, students' self-checking and monitoring of their own work has a positive impact on the formation of competencies.

A student's independent thinking may consist of the following stages:

1. The appearance of the problem in the field of student perception.
2. The student's understanding of the essence of the issue, problem, assignment.
3. The emergence of information or images similar to them.
4. Reduction of imagination and memory materials, continuous birth of assumptions (hypotheses).
5. Step-by-step verification of assumptions or their confirmation of authenticity.
6. Emergence and improvement of a new hypothesis.
7. Secondary testing of hypotheses (second confirmation)
8. Finding a solution to a problem, task, problem (Solution).
9. Continuation of involuntary mental actions (relative duration of thoughts), etc.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that there are many opportunities for independent education in the modern era due to the rapid advancement of science and technology, the widespread use of contemporary information and communication systems, the quick updating of scientific knowledge across a range of fields, and the daily changes in techniques and technology. Additionally, the development of methodologies is necessary for the creation and use of electronic textbooks. Electronic textbooks designed for foreign

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language instruction should focus on fostering students' creativity, offering them the chance to learn independently, and enabling them to explore new information.

The productivity of a student is closely associated with the independence of his thought process. A student's thinking is considered productive if, within a given time frame, they solve theoretical and practical problems and offer insightful and original ideas, thoughts, and recommendations for a particular field. The standard for gauging the productivity of a student's thought process is a fair appraisal of the amount and caliber of mental work completed during the allotted time.

When a student considers everyday topics, he is not constrained by their outward manifestations and instead seeks to distill the essence of happenings and derive a general social law from everyday reality. Without a doubt, the students' independent thought has opened up previously undiscovered and unrealized possibilities, and their complete disclosure helps to advance science and technology. Since innovation is a byproduct of human intelligence development in any organization, the advancement of science and technology primarily depends on the independent thought of a specialist. Mature students go through stages in their physical, moral, and mental development.

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